

Title: Aldehyde, Ketones and Carboxylic Acid for NEET and JEE students in One Page

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Abstract

In organic chemistry, aldehydes, ketones, and carboxylic acids are important functional groups that connect aliphatic and aromatic molecules through a variety of oxidation and reduction reactions. This review thoroughly examines their structure, methods of synthesis, physical and chemical properties, and reaction mechanisms, highlighting their synthetic and industrial importance. Nucleophilic addition, oxidation-reduction interconversions, and condensation reactions like the aldol and Cannizzaro reactions are given special attention. The mind mapping method puts these reactions and mechanical pathways together in a way that helps people grasp how functional groups change.

Key Words

Aldehydes, Ketones, Carboxylic acids, Nucleophilic addition, Aldol condensation, Acidity, Mind mapping

PREPARATIONS

- Oxidation of 1° alcohols**

$$RCH_2OH \xrightarrow[(ii) H_3O^+]{(i) alk. KMnO_4} R - COOH$$
- Hydrolysis of Nitriles and Amides**

$$R - C \equiv N + 2H_2O \xrightarrow[OH^-]{H^+} RCOOH + N_3H$$
- Hydrolysis of Esters**

$$RCOOR' + H_2O \xrightarrow{H^+} RCOOH + R'OH$$
- From Grignard Reagent**

$$CO_2 + RMgBr \xrightarrow[H^+, H_2O]{Dry ether} RCOOH + Mg(OH)Br$$

PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

- Physical State:** Polar substances soluble in organic solvents.
- Acidity:** The acidic character is due to the presence of resonance.

$$R - \overset{\overset{O}{\parallel}}{C} - \overset{\ominus}{O} - H \longleftrightarrow R - \overset{\overset{O}{\parallel}}{C} - \overset{\oplus}{O} - H$$
- Boiling Points:** High boiling point due to intermolecular hydrogen bonding.

COMPARISON OF MELTING AND BOILING POINT OF AROMATIC AND ALIPHATIC ACID

- Melting Point and Boiling Point of aromatic acid greater than aliphatic acid.

CHEMICAL PROPERTIES

- Esterification**

$$RCOOH + R'OH \rightleftharpoons RCOOR' + H_2O$$
- Ring Substitution in Aromatic Acids:** COOH group is deactivating and meta directing.

- Reduction of Carboxylic Acid**

$$R - \overset{\overset{O}{\parallel}}{C} - OH \xrightarrow[(ii) H_3O^+]{(i) LiAlH_4/ether} R - CH_2OH$$
- Decarboxylation of Carboxylic Acid**

$$R - \overset{\overset{O}{\parallel}}{C} - OH \xrightarrow[CaO]{NaOH} R - H + Na_2CO_3$$
- Reaction involving cleavage of -OH group**

$$R - \overset{\overset{O}{\parallel}}{C} - OH \begin{cases} \rightarrow R - \overset{\overset{O}{\parallel}}{C} - NH_2 \\ \rightarrow R - COCl \\ \rightarrow (R - CO)_2O \end{cases}$$
- Hell-volhard Zelin'sky Reaction**

$$R - CH_2 - OH \xrightarrow[(ii) H_2O]{(i) X_2, Red P} R - CH(x)COOH$$

ACIDIC ORDER

Carboxylic Acid > Phenol > Alcohol

ALDEHYDE, KETONES AND CARBOXYLIC ACID

PREPARATIONS

- Oxidation of alcohol**

$$1^\circ \text{ Alcohol} \xrightarrow{K_2Cr_2O_7 + H_2SO_4} \text{Aldehyde}$$

$$2^\circ \text{ Alcohol} \xrightarrow{K_2Cr_2O_7 + H_2SO_4} \text{Ketone}$$

$$R - CH_2OH \xrightarrow{K_2Cr_2O_7 + H_2SO_4} RCHO + H_2O$$

$$R - \underset{\underset{OH}{|}}{C}(OH)R' \xrightarrow{K_2Cr_2O_7 + H_2SO_4} R - CO - R' + H_2O$$
- Ozonolysis of alkenes**

$$CH_3 - CH = CH - CH_3 + O_3 \xrightarrow{H_2O, Zn} 2CH_3CHO$$
- From Gem-Dihalides:**

$$R - \underset{\underset{Cl}{|}}{C} - Cl \xrightarrow[Or Ba(OH)_2]{aq. KOH} R - \overset{\overset{O}{\parallel}}{C} - H$$

(Aldehyde when R' = H)
 (Ketone when R' = alkyl group)
- Hydroboration Oxidation of Alkynes**

$$R - C \equiv C - H \xrightarrow[THF]{B_2H_6} R - \overset{\overset{H}{|}}{C} = \overset{\overset{H}{|}}{C} - H$$

$$\xrightarrow{H_2O_2, OH^-} R - \overset{\overset{H}{|}}{C} - \overset{\overset{H}{|}}{C} - H$$
- Rosenmund Reduction**

$$R - \overset{\overset{O}{\parallel}}{C} - Cl \xrightarrow{H_2, Pd - BaSO_4} R - \overset{\overset{O}{\parallel}}{C} - H$$

DISTINCTION TEST FOR CARBOXYLIC ACID

- Brisk effervescence of CO₂ gas with NaHCO₃
- Gives buff coloured ppt. with FeCl₃

ALDEHYDES AND KETONES

- GENERAL FORMULA**
 - Aldehyde:**

$$R - \overset{\overset{O}{\parallel}}{C} - H$$

where R is alkyl and H is Hydrogen.
 - Ketones**

$$R - \overset{\overset{O}{\parallel}}{C} - R'$$

where R and R' can be same or different.
- CLASSIFICATION**
 - Aliphatic
 - Aromatic
- CHEMICAL PROPERTIES**
 - Aldehyde > Ketones
 - Reactivity $\propto \frac{1}{\text{Steric factor and electronic factor}}$
 - Nucleophilic Addition-reaction**

$$>C=O + CN^- \rightleftharpoons >C(OH)CN$$

$$>C=O + NaHSO_3 \rightarrow >C(OH)SO_3Na$$

$$>C=O + H_2N-Z \rightarrow >C=N-Z + H_2O$$
 - Clemmensen Reduction:**

$$>C=O \xrightarrow[HCl]{Zn - Hg} >CH_2 + H_2O$$
 - Wolff-Kishner reduction**

$$>C=O \xrightarrow[KOH/ethyl glycol]{(i) NH_2 - NH_2} >CH_2 + N_2$$
 - Aldol Condensation**

$$2CH_3CHO \rightarrow CH_3CH(OH)CH_2CHO$$

$$\downarrow \Delta - H_2O$$

$$CH_3 - CH = CH - CHO$$
 - Cannizzaro reaction**

$$2HCHO \xrightarrow{Conc. KOH} CH_3OH + HCOOK$$
- PHYSICAL PROPERTIES**
 - Odour:** Lower Aldehyde have an unpleasant odour.
 - Physical State:** HCHO is a gas. All other aldehyde and ketone upto C₁₁ are volatile liquids.
 - Solubility:** Larger Carbonyl compounds are soluble in water due to the formation of H-bond.
 - Boiling Point and Melting Point:** Boiling Point or Melting point \propto Molecular weight

$$\propto \frac{1}{\text{Branching}}$$
 - Due to electron donating alkyl group ketones have higher boiling point than aldehyde.**
 - Reactivity:** It depends on the nature of alkyl group. Smaller the group, more reactive will be compound.

DISTINCTION TEST FOR ALDEHYDE

TEST	ALDEHYDE	KETONES
Schiff's reagent	Pink Colour	No colour
Fehling's Solution	Red ppt.	No ppt.
Tollen's reagent	Silver Mirror	No ppt.

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